

Personal Data

Tobias Cornelius Hinse, B.Sc., M.Sc., Ph.D., dr. habil.

Adjunct Professor at University of Southern Denmark

Email: toch@sdu.dk

Citizen of:	Federal Republic of Germany.
Gender:	Male.
Current employer:	University of Southern Denmark.
Education:	Germany, Denmark, United Kingdom and Poland.
Language:	German, Danish and English (for all: fluent in writing and speaking; bilingual in Danish and German).
Ph.D. degree award:	December 2010.
Dr. habil. degree award ¹ :	September 2019.
Number of publications ² :	263 (non-refereed); 160 (refereed).
Total refereed citations ² :	5845.
Hirsh H-index ² :	41.
Hirsh H-index (WoS):	39.
www:	https://portal.findresearcher.sdu.dk/en/persons/toch
Past academic activities:	https://zenodo.org/records/10907593
Zenodo:	https://zenodo.org/searchq=Hinse&l=list&p=5&s=20&sort=bestmatch

Education

- Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland. Habilitation (Dr. habil.) (2019).
- Queen's University Belfast / Armagh Observatory, UK. Astronomy, Ph.D. (2010).

¹ Likely, the equivalent academic degree in Denmark is the 'dr. scient.' degree.

² Source: NASA/Astronomical Data Service: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/>

- University of Copenhagen, Denmark. Physics/Astronomy, M.Sc. (2006).
- Borningschool / high-school in Ulfborg, Aarhus & Copenhagen (Gymnasium & HF).
- 9 years of basic education, Germany.

Employment Time-line & Research Experience

April 2024 – now:

Adjunct Professor, University of Southern Denmark.

Research in astronomy and astrophysics, extrasolar planets, eclipsing binaries, solar system physics, observational astronomy and numerical explorations of dynamical systems at the Department for Physics and Chemistry (FKF) / SDU-Galaxy / CP3-Origins as well as observational astrophysics and related data science activities. Science communication with strong focus on high school and KASTEM students in collab with the Department of Science Education / KU. Development of didactical FysikLab student hands-on exercises and experiments. Application of citizen science projects in science communication as a STEM-based active learning environment. Supervision and co-supervising of undergraduate students (ISA & BSc) as well as final-year high-school (national / international baccalaureat) students (SRP/SOP/SSO final year essays) and udskolingslever (praktikforløb). Teaching and co-teaching of various astronomy and astrophysics (graduate and undergrad) courses at FKF. Supervision of students in relation to building a danish camera network for the detection of atmospheric meteor/fireballs in national airspace as well as training students within astrodynamics and image data processing as part of the danish-led Máni lunar space-mission (KU/DTU/SDU/AU/AAU/ESA). Involvement with the FUT telescope operated at Aarhus University (AU) and participant in the planned STEP space-telescope (PI: Hans Kjeldsen/AU). Continued astrophysical observations with the Danish telescope at the ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile.

Aug. 2023 – March 2024:

Research assistant, University of Southern Denmark.

Research in astronomy and astrophysics, extrasolar planets and numerical explorations of dynamical systems at the Department for Physics and Chemistry, SDU-Galaxy. Science communication with strong focus on high-school students. Development of didactical FysikLAB student exercises. Application of citizen science projects in science communication as a STEM-based active learning environment. Co-supervising undergraduate students (ISA) as well as final-year high-school students (SRP/SOP/SSO). Teaching of Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) course at SDUB mandatory for SDU enrolled PhD students. Continued astrophysical observations with the Danish telescope at the ESO/La Silla observatory in Chile.

Aug. 2022 – July 2023:

Research Librarian, University of Southern Denmark.

One year time-limited position. Teaching within the topics of Research Data Management, Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) incl. OpenScience, OpenAccess, OpenData and FAIR data principles. Public outreach and general support for dissemination of science, re-

search and bibliometrics. Support / participation in ‘Citizens Science’ in astrophysics and FABLAB / MakerSpace activities aimed at STEM students. Bibliometric expertise within physics and astronomy. Research in astrophysics within the fields of instrumentation and observational astronomy, extrasolar planetary science and solar system physics.

Sep. 2021 – Aug. 2023: Associate Professor at Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland.

Time-limited position for two years. Research only activities, no teaching obligations with the department for Physics, Astronomy and Informatics and Centre of Excellence in Astrophysics and Astro-chemistry. Research and supervision activities are within the field of extrasolar planets and Solar System dynamics as well as observational astrophysics.

Jul. 2018 – Aug. 2021: Research Professor at Chungnam National University, South Korea.

Research, teaching and supervision responsibilities in the department for astronomy and space science in the area of astronomical data analysis and introductory astronomy & astrophysics and related space science. Position was tenured-track and supported by the Korea National Research Foundation (NRF) and ‘Brain Korea 21’ (BK21) research program. Pre-pandemic remote online-based e-teaching and student supervision duties. Co-supervision of M.Sc. students Mr. N. Park and Mr. Ha-Eun Kim. Main supervisor to Ph.D. candidate Mrs. C. Kim Ly. Member of scientific organizing committee (SOC) and co-chair of an international conference. Invited workshop lecturer. Research & education (R&E) teaching. Occasional teaching substitute for colleagues. Popular science public outreach talks. Workshop teaching assistant at Caltech.

Sep. 2019: Habilitation from Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland.

Award of the academic degree ‘Doktora Habilitowanego’ (title: dr. habil.). Likely corresponds to ‘dr. scient’ in Denmark.

Oct. 2015 – Dec. 2015: Visiting Scientist at Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland.

Short-term visiting scientist to initiate and discuss a long-term research project within dynamics of extrasolar planetary systems. Host: Prof. Dr. K. Goździewski. Institute colloquium given.

Sep. 2015 – Jun. 2018: Senior Research Scientist, KASI, South Korea.

Promotion to senior research scientist. Continuation of main research activities within the field of extrasolar planets, N -body astro-dynamics, numerical celestial mechanics and statistical data analysis and data modeling. R & E teaching, workshop teaching assistant at Caltech, M.Sc. & Ph.D. co-supervision and public outreach activities. Invited workshop lecturer. Workshop teaching assistant at Caltech.

Mar. 2015 – Dec. 2015: Adjunct supervisor at University of Southern Queensland, Australia.

Short-term adjunct scientist at the faculty of health, engineering and sciences (USQ) to serve as an external co-supervisor for Ph.D. candidate Mr. Jeremy Woods. Mr. Wood was enrolled as a distance-learning student. Supervision mainly via online media.

Jan. 2015 – Aug. 2015: Post-doctoral Research Fellow, KASI, South Korea.

Promotion to research fellow at Korea Astronomy & Space Science Institute. Continuation of research within the field of extrasolar planets, astro-dynamics, observational astronomy and astrostatistics/statistical data analysis. R & E teaching. Participation of national science competition. 2014 best post-doctoral research award. Mentoring summer-school internship student. M.Sc. & Ph.D. co-supervisor. Workshop teaching assistant at Caltech.

Nov. 2012 – Dec. 2012: Visiting scientist at University of Hawaii at Manoa. USA.

Short-term visiting scientist at the Institute for Astronomy to initiate and discuss a long-term research project within circumbinary planetary systems. Host: Prof. N. Haghighipour.

Jan. 2012 – Dec. 2014: KRCF Young Scientist Research Fellow, KASI, South Korea.

Award of competitive 2+1 year KRCF post-doctoral fellowship. Continuation of research within the field of extrasolar planets, circumbinary transiting planets, astro-dynamics and astronomical data analysis and modelling. 2012 & 2014 best post-doctoral research award + 2012 best group-achievement award. R & E teaching. 2014 high-school silver medal award (Young Scientist Award competition). Workshop teaching assistant at Caltech.

Jan. 2011 – Dec. 2011: Post-doctoral research scientist, KASI, South Korea.

Start of first post-doctoral position at Korea Astronomy & Space Science Institute. Initiated research in astro-dynamics with application to circumbinary extrasolar planets, transiting planets and statistical data modelling and analysis. Main supervisor: Prof. Dr. J. W. Lee. Workshop teaching assistant at Caltech.

Aug. 2007 – Dec. 2010: Ph.D. from Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom.

Start of research work towards a Ph.D. degree. Main supervisor: Dr. Apostolos A. Christou. Field of research: astro-dynamics, numerical celestial mechanics with application to irregular satellites of giant solar system planets. Enrolment at Queen's University Belfast. I carried out long-term and statistically valid, large-scale N -body particle simulations to assess the long-term phase-space diffusion properties of orbital elements of natural satellites. The analysis involved the numerical computation of the maximum Lyapunov exponent to assess chaotic time evolution. Implementation of a Fortran-based / OpenMPI parallel computer code for the numerical solution of the equations of motion and associated variational equations. Phase-space diffusion properties were also investigated by the application of Fourier-based analysis techniques. Parallel research: extrasolar planets, data reduction and statistical data modelling and follow-up observations of transiting planets using the high-precision photometric telescope defocus technique. *Ph.D. training 1:* project- and risk-management training by Fistral Training and Consultancy Ltd

(www.fistraltraining.com). Obtained entry exam qualification of sitting the CAPM (Certified Associate in Project Management) certificate exam. *Ph.D. training 2*: communication, presentation and laboratory safety training, teaching assistant training, numerous popular science and public outreach activities.

Jun. 2006 – Jun. 2007: Student research assistant, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Employed student research assistant at the Instrument Centre for Danish Astrophysics, University of Copenhagen. Training of visiting students on practical astronomy and technical telescope operation and real-time data reduction techniques to ensure data integrity and quality. Applied for Ph.D. fellowships at International Max Planck Research School (Göttingen) and Armagh Observatory. Both institutions offered me a Ph.D. research fellowship.

Aug. 2001 – Jun. 2002: Erasmus student at German Aerospace Center, Berlin, Germany.

Erasmus visiting student at Technische Universität Berlin and Institut für Weltraumsensorik und Planetenerkundung, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR). Supervisors: Prof. Dr. Heike Rauer and Dr. Anders Erikson. Project: literature review within the field of extrasolar planets, astro-dynamics and numerical celestial mechanics.

Aug. 1998 – Jun. 2006: B.Sc. & M.Sc. from University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Enrolled in the bachelor- and master-degree program in physics-astronomy at the Niels Bohr Institute, Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Denmark. I followed lectures in applied mathematics, physics and astronomy including course work in natural philosophy, informatics and laboratory didactics and safety practice. M.Sc. thesis advisor: Prof. Uffe G. Jørgensen. M.Sc. thesis project received highest score. M.Sc. thesis work resulted in a 2008 research paper.

Aug. 1994 – Jun. 1997: High-school education, Denmark.

Enrolled at 'Nørrevold Gymnasium & HF' high-school located in Copenhagen, Denmark. 3 years of basic high-school training leading towards a national university entry exam. Focus was on subjects within the field of natural sciences (A-level math, physics and biology).

Aug. 1991 – May 1994: International boarding school, Denmark.

Enrolled at an international school in Denmark. The school offered practical education at high-school level in combination with international travelling and student exchange programs. Highlights were short-term educational trips to Mexico, USA, Turkey and Norway.

Feb. 1975 – Jun. 1991: Basic education, Schleswig-Holstein, Germany.

Born in Vollerwiek (Eiderstedt/Nordfriesland). I visited schools part of the Danish minority in Germany (Dänische Minderheit in Südschleswig) starting from the Danish kindergarten in Tönning with elementary schools in Tönning (Uffe-Skolen) and Husum (Husum Danske Skole). I obtained my first personal computer (Schneider CPC 464) in 1987 resulting in me learning the *BASIC* programming language.

Research Projects & Scientific Interests

Solar System Dynamics & Evolution (Theory)

- Dynamical evolution of giant planet irregular satellites.
- Dynamical evolution of small Solar System objects.
- Dynamical evolution and physical properties of small-body (Chariklo) ring system.

Solar System Dynamics & Evolution (Observation)

- Follow-up observation and astrometry of Jovian irregular satellites.
- Photometric follow-up observations of asteroids and comets.
- Meteor detection & astrometric orbit determination and characterization of meteor showers.
- High-speed/high-cadence EMCCD photometry of Solar System minor body occultation events.

Sky-Monitoring/Detection/Instrumentation

- Development of a proto-type double-station meteor video-detection network in South Korea (BOAO & SOAO), Research & Education project (<http://meteor.kasi.re.kr>).
- High-speed video astronomy using a monochrome light-sensitive CCD.
- Atmospheric meteor detection, satellite detection, monitoring of planets.
- Spectroscopy of meteor events (Research & Education 2019/2020/2021).

Extrasolar Planets (Theory)

- Dynamics planetary systems & habitability of Earth-like planets.
- Modeling & detection of extra-solar circumbinary companions/planets.
- Detecting additional planets by transit-timing variations.
- Prediction of additional planets from classic n-body dynamics.
- Lyapunov instability time-scales of (transiting) multi-planet systems.

Extrasolar Planets (Observation)

- Photometric follow-up and light-curve modeling of planets by transit method.
- Detecting planets around binary star systems by light-travel time effect method & additional timing techniques (eclipse timing variations).
- Detecting planets by the gravitational microlensing technique.
- Microlensing modeling and parallax measurements.

Eclipsing Binaries (Observation)

- Photometric observations of short-period eclipsing binary star systems.
- High-cadence EMCCD photometric observations of cataclysmic binary star system (in progress).
- Determination of absolute dimensions of late-type eclipsing binary systems (in progress).
- Light- & radial velocity data modeling.
- Strömngren *uvby- β* photometry and calibration of stellar atmospheric properties.

Astronomical Spectroscopy (Data Reduction & Analysis)

- Data reduction of ESO/FEROS (ESO/Fibre-fed Extended Range Optical Spectrograph) spectra using ESO-MIDAS data analysis and extraction facility.
- FEROS data analysis with IRAF (in progress).
- FEROS data analysis with Python (in progress).
- DFOSC astronomical data / image analysis and processing.

Astronomical Photometry (Data Reduction & Analysis)

- Classic CCD differential photometry using various telescopes.
- High-speed EMCCD photometry.
- Video-astronomy with low-light sensitive cameras.
- Data analysis using IDL, Python, Fortran, C, C++

Awards, Grants & International Recognitions

- Nominated by SDU students for the 2024/2025 Faculty of Science Teaching Award, University of Southern Denmark.
- 2025 Carlsbergfoundation grant as PI: ~100.000 DKK. (EUR ~13,500). Oct. 2025.
- 2025 Wieth-Knudsen grant as PI: ~75.000 DKK. (EUR ~10,000). March. 2025.
- 2025 Carlsbergfoundation grant as PI: ~100.000 DKK. (EUR ~13,500). Jan. 2025.
- 2024: Supervisor to Student Best Poster Award. <https://zenodo.org/records/13832515>
- 2024: Honorary naming of solar system minor planet '10723 Tobiashinse' by the International Astronomical Union (IAU), <https://zenodo.org/records/11317114> .
- 2023 Novo Nordisk grant as Co-PI: 2.500.000 DKK. (EUR ~335,000). April 2024. I wrote 90% of the original application.
- 2021 Europlanet 2024 telescope operation grant. EUR ~5,000.

- 2019 – 2021 Research & Education Award 1st rank, Korea Regional first-stage National Science Competition, Daejeon Science Highschool/CNU. **US\$ 5,000**
- 2019 – 2022 NRF (National Research Foundation) research award for 2019 – 2022, Republic of Korea. **US\$ 250,000.**
- 2015 R&E Award, 1st rank, Korea Regional (Daejeon City) Pre-Selection National Science Competition, Daejeon, Daejeon Science Highschool/KASI. **US\$ 2,000**
- 2014 R&E Award, 2nd rank (silver medal), 1st Daejeon Science Highschool Young Scientist Award Competition, Daejeon Science Highschool/KASI.
- 2014 R&E program, KASI-Daejeon Science Highschool, **US\$ 12,000.**
- 2014 Best KASI Post-doctoral Research Scientist of the Year Award (KASI), **US\$ 1,000.**
- 2012 Best KASI Post-doctoral Research Scientist of the Year Award (KASI), **US\$ 1,000.**
- 2012 Best Group Achievement Award (KASI, Group PI: Prof. Dr. J. W. Lee – what a loser!).
- NORDITA travel grant (2006 Astrobiology Workshop, Finland). Amount: **US\$ 1,000.**
- ESO/La Silla observing travel grant (University of Copenhagen). Amount: **US\$ 3,500.**
- ANGLES travel grant (2008 Microlensing Meeting, UK). Amount: **US\$ 1,600.**
- Various travel awards from Armagh Observatory, UK. Amount: **US\$ 2,000.**
- 2010 Lyot/IMCCE travel grant. Amount: **US\$ 1,000.**
- 2010 travel grant from JPL/NExSci (Sagan Workshop). Amount: **US\$ 1,000.**
- 2012 travel grant from JPL/NExSci (Sagan Workshop). Amount: **US\$ 1,000.**
- IAU 2012 Beijing travel grant. Grant number: GA 922. Amount: **US\$ 2,600.**
- 2012 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2012-1-410-02. Amount: **US\$ 5,000.**
- 2012 Research stay travel grant. Uni. of Hawaii-Manoa. Amount: **US\$ 3,000.**
- 2013 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2013-9-400-00. Amount: **US\$ 5,000.**
- IAUS 299 (Canada) travel grant. Grant number: n/a. Amount: **US\$ 2,700.**
- 2013 Observing trip (local) travel support, Uni. of Cop., Amount: **US\$ 1,600.**
- 2014 travel grant JPL/NExSci (Carl Sagan Workshop). Amount: **US\$ ~1,000.**

- 2014 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2014-1-400-06. Amount: **US\$ 5,000.**
- 2015 travel grant JPL/NExSci (Carl Sagan Workshop). Amount: **US\$ ~1,000.**
- 2015 ESO/La Silla observing travel grant (Uni. of Cop.). Amount: **US\$ 3,500.**
- 2015 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2015-1-850-04. Amount: **US\$ 5,000.**
- 2016 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2016-1-832-01. Amount: **US\$ 10,000.**
- 2017 KASI travel grant. Grant number: 2017-1-830-03. Amount: **US\$ 10,000.**

Professional Activities

- Member of M.Sc. review committee board for MSc student Vincente Moldonado, University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.
- Member of Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) at “TNU/SGI International Summer School of Research and Exploration in Astronomy 2024”, Tay Nguyen University, BMT City, Vietnam.
- Member of Local Organizing Committee (LOC) for the National Space Conference, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, October 2023.
- Member of Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) for session “*Astronomy in the era of LEO satellite constellations: avoidance, mitigation, and dark and quiet sky protection*” at the EAS 2023 meeting (https://eas.unige.ch/EAS_meeting/).
- Book review for MIT Press: “Moving Planet Around”. Published by MIT Press in 2020/2021.
- Member of M.Sc. review committee board for MSc student Pía Cortés Zuleta, University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.
- Grant-proposal reviewer for the Polish National Science Center.
- Member of Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) at “The 2nd Recontres du Vietnam on Exoplanetary Science 2018” conference, Quy Nhon, Vietnam.
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Astronomy & Astrophysics* (A&A).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy* (CMDA).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* (MNRAS).

- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Australia* (PASA).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Astronomical Journal* (AJ).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Astrophysical Journal* (ApJ).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Advances in Space Research Journal* (ASR).
- Registered / appointed **referee** for *Icarus Journal*.
- External reviewer for European OPTICON observing proposals (TAC).
- Member of the Danish Astronomical Union, Denmark. Thank you SDU for welcoming me!
- Member of the Danish Physical Society, Denmark. Thank you SDU for welcoming me!
- Former member of the Kepler Eclipsing Binary Working Group, USA
- Former member of the Korea Astrophysical Society, South Korea. Good I left that place!
- Former member of the Korea Space Science Society, South Korea. Good I left that place!

Teaching, Lecturing & Student Supervising

- Co-teaching various undergraduate, graduate and post-graduate courses at University of Southern Denmark and University Library (SDUB).
- Supervision of various SDU and danish secondary, high-school students. Science communication with focus on STEM-based active learning (University of Southern Denmark 2023, 2024, 2025).
- Lecturing (online) introductory astronomy at Chungnam National University (2019/2020/2021).
- Research & Education teaching-supervision in South Korea (various years).
- Workshop-lecturer at the “TNU/SGI International Summer School of Research and Exploration in Astronomy 2024”, Tay Nguyen University, BMT City, Vietnam.
- Workshop-lecturer at “The 7th Vietnam School of Astrophysics. Topic: “Planetary Science”, ICISE, Quy Nohn, Vietnam.
- Workshop-lecturer at “The 2nd Recontres du Vietnam on Exoplanetary Science 2018” conference, Quy Nohn, Vietnam.

- Organizing public outreach activities (DK, UK, South Korea, Germany, Poland).
- External co-supervisor/advisor for PhD/MSc students in UK, Turkey, Denmark, Chile, S. Korea.
- Popular science communicator on primary/high-school level (Denmark, Germany, South Korea, Poland).
- Tutor and assisting teacher at hands-on exercise at the Carl Sagan Summer School Workshop 2012, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 @ NexSci/IPAC/California Institute of Technology, California, Pasadena, USA.
- PI of Research & Education (R&E) 2014/2015 program (Daejeon Science Highschool/KASI). Project title: “*Setup, testing and operation of an automatic double-station meteor detection network*”, S. Korea.
- Adjunct scientist at University of Southern Queensland (USQ), Australia. PhD co-supervisor for Jeremy Wood. Thesis title: “*The Dynamics of Ringed Small Bodies*”. 2015 - 2018. Main supervisor: prof. J. Horner & prof. S. C. Marsden.
- Co-supervisor of M.Sc. student Sanne Hardis, University of Copenhagen, 2011-2012. Thesis title: “*The Transiting Exoplanet GJ 1214b*”, Denmark. (main supervisor: Prof. Uffe G. Jørgensen).
- Co-supervisor of M.Sc. student Ekrem Murat Esmer, Ankara University, Department of Astronomy and Space Sciences, Ankara, Turkey, 2014 – 2015. Thesis title: „*Exoplanet discovery in Multi-Stellar Systems with the Timing Technique*”. Main supervisor: prof. Selim O. Selam.
- Co-supervisor of Ph.D. student Aswin Sekhar, 2011 – 2014. Armagh Observatory/Queens University Belfast, UK. Thesis title: „*Evolution of Halley-type Comets and Meteoroid Streams*”. 2014. Main supervisor: Dr D. J. Asher.
- Research mentor for summer student Anna Carolina Sirico. Research internship June/July 2015. Project “*Implementation of an algorithm to determine absolute dimensions of a transiting extrasolar planet by least-squares minimization*”.
- Co-supervisor of M.Sc. student Beom-Kyu Choi at Kyung-buk National University. Thesis title: “*Gravitational Simulation Study for the Extrasolar system: EPIC 201367065 (K2- 3)*”. Daegu, South Korea (main supervisor: Prof. Tae-soek Yoon).
- Co-supervisor of Ph.D. student Ekrem Murat Esmer, Ankara University, Department of Astronomy and Space Sciences, Ankara, Turkey, 2018 – 2021. Thesis title: „*Orbital Stabilities of the Substellar Objects in Multibody Systems*”. Main supervisor: prof. Selim O. Selam.

Academic References

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... there are many more scholars at professor level who are willing to issue a letter of reference.

Publications, Talks & Conference Contributions

Publications published and in preparation (listing 1st, 2nd and 3rd author papers only). Currently 45 refereed (ADS) papers. Errata publications not included.

- XX. Baştürk, O. & **Hinse, T. C.**, et al. 2026, “*High-precision photometry by telescope defocussing. The transiting planet Qatar-2b and its star spots*”, MNRAS, in preparation.
45. **Hinse, T. C.** & Baştürk, O. et al. 2024, “*Absolute dimensions of solar-type eclipsing binaries. NY Hya: A test for magnetic stellar evolution models*”, A&A, 687, 116.
44. Zotos, E. E., Moneer, E. M., **Hinse, T. C.**, 2024, “*Classification of Planetary Motion around Super-Jupiters and Brown Dwarf*”, Universe, 10, 138.
43. **Hinse, T. C.** Dorch, S. F., et al, 2023, “*How Tycho Brahe’s recordings in 1572 support SN 1572 as a type I(a) supernova*”, FrASS, vol. 10, id. 1255481.
42. Southworth, J., Barker, A. J., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2022, “*A search for transit timing variations in the HATS-18 planetary system*”, MNRAS, 515, 3212.
41. Wood, J. and **Hinse, T. C.**, 2021, “*The Transformation of Centaurs into Jupiter-family Comets*”, ApJ, 929, 157.
40. Zotos, E. E., Albalawi, H., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2021, “*Quantitative orbit classification of the planar restricted three-body problem with application to the motion of a satellite around Jupiter*”, Chaos Solitons and Fractals (CSF), 152, 111444.
39. Esmer, E. M., Baştürk, O., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2021, “*Revisiting the analysis of HW Virginis eclipse timing data. I. A frequentist data modeling approach and a dynamical stability analysis*”, A&A, 648, 85.
38. Herath, M. & **Hinse, T. C.**, et al., 2019, “*Two temperate sub-Neptunes transiting the star EPIC 212737443*”, MNRAS, 488, 536.
37. Wang, Y.-H., Wang, S., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2019, “*Transiting Exoplanet Monitoring Project (TEMP). V. Transit Follow-Up for the HAT-P-9b, HAT-P-32b, and HAT-P-36b*”, AJ, 157, 82.
36. Wood, J., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, S. C., 2018, “*Measuring the severity of close encounters between ringed small bodies and planets*”, MNRAS, 480, 4183.
35. Wang, X., Wang, S., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2018, “*Transiting Exoplanet Monitoring Project (TEMP). IV. Refined System Parameters, Transit Timing Variations and Orbital Stability of the Transiting Planetary System HAT-P-25*”, PASP, 130f, 4401.
34. Wang, X., Wang, S., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2018, “*Refined System Parameters, Transit Timing Variations and Orbital Stability of the Transiting Planetary System HAT-P-25*”, PASP, 130f, 4401.
33. Bachelet, E. , **Hinse, T. C.** & Street, R., 2018, “*Measuring the microlensing parallax from various space observatories*”, AJ, 155, 191.
32. Wood, J., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, S. C., 2018, “*The Dynamical History of 2060 Chiron and Its Proposed Ring System*”, AJ, 155, 2.

31. **Hinse, T. C.**, Kim, W.-K., Ahn, S.-H., et al., 2017, “*Proto-type installation of a double-station system for the optical-video-detection and orbital characterisation of a meteor/fireball in South Korea*”, PKAS, 32, 381.
30. Wood, J., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, Stephen C., 2017, “*The Dynamical History of Chariklo and Its Rings*”, AJ, 153, 245.
29. **Hinse, T. C.**, Han, Wonyong, Yoon, Joh-Na, 2015, “*Photometric Defocus Observations of Transiting Extrasolar Planets*”, JASS, 32, 21.
28. Lee, J. W., Hong Kyeongsoo, **Hinse, T. C.**, 2015, “*The Kepler Eclipsing System KIC 5621294 and Its Substellar Companion*”, AJ, 149, 93.
27. **Hinse, T. C.**, Goździewski, K., Kostov, V., Haghighipour, N., 2015, “*Predicting a third planet in the Kepler-47 circumbinary system*”, ApJ, 799, 88.
26. Lee, J. W., **Hinse, T. C.**, Youn, J.-H., Han, W., 2014, “*The Pulsating sdB+M Eclipsing System NY Virginis and its Circumbinary Planets*”, MNRAS, 445, 2331.
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Conference & Workshop contributions (talks & posters)

2025

Wadowski, S., Eriksen, R. L. & **Hinse, T. C.** (supervisor), 2025, “Monte-Carlo ray-tracing simulations to demonstrate astrophysical gravitational lensing effects: Simple numerical experiments to enable hands-on simulations of gravitational lensing in the class-room”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Vejle, May 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15496372>. Poster.

Kromann Larsen, L. & **Hinse, T. C.** (supervisor), 2025, “Miniature Robot Telescope model for Educational Learning”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Vejle, May 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15525134>. Poster.

Amarsanaa, B., **Hinse, T. C.**, Jakobsen, J. E. & Dybkjær, R. H., 2025, “Máni@SDU: SDU-Galaxy and AAU SATLAB's ESA-GODOT Software and Astrodynamics Workshop (July 2025)”, workshop held at FKF/SDU-Galaxy, July 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15805169>. 1-day activity.

Hein Pedersem, J. & **Hinse, T. C.** (supervisor), 2025, “The Modern Eddington Experiment”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Vejle, May 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15534207>. Poster.

Christensen, F. H. D., Comerón, S. & **Hinse, T. C.** (supervisor), 2025, “Dark Matter in the Coma Cluster”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Vejle, May 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15496593>. Poster.

Amarsanaa, B. & **Hinse, T. C.**, 2025, “Lunar Transfer and Perturbation Analysis for Proposed ESA Máni Mission: Comparing Hohmann, EML1 and ESL1 Trajectories with ESA GODOT”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Vejle, May 2025, <https://zenodo.org/records/15496340>. Poster.

2024

Christiansen, N. P., Kim Vu, H., **Hinse, T. C.**, et al. 2024, “The Universe Unveiled: The FUT Telescope's Imaging Capabilities”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Roskilde, May 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/11312879>, Poster.

Forskov, Eriksen, N. & **Hinse, T. C.**, et al. 2024, “NASA's GMAT: a software tool-kit for general space-mission design and space-craft trajectory analysis”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting (ADAM), Roskilde, May 2024, <https://zenodo.org/records/11276605>, Poster.

2023

Longa-Peña, P. & **Hinse, T. C.**, et al. 2023, “LEO satellites: "photobombing astronomy images"”, Danish National Space-Science Conference, 2023, November 2023, Odense, Denmark, <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8405077>, Poster.

Hinse, T. C., 2023, “SDU Project: Astrobiology review-poster for the 2023 national youth space and national space conference”, Danish National Space Conference, November 2023, Odense, Denmark, <https://zenodo.org/records/10176241>, Poster.

Hinse, T. C., workshop organizer, 2023, “Citizen Science Workshop: "The hunt for stardust - find your own micrometeorite"”, <https://zenodo.org/records/13980904>.

Sebastian B. Bjørnskov & **Hinse, T. C.**, 2023, “Direkte eftersøgning af liv på andre (exo)planeter”, Danish National Space Conference, 2023, November 2023, Odense, Denmark, <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10149860>, Poster.

Hinse, T. C. et al., 2023, “Citizen Science Projects in Astronomy and Astrophysics 2023”, Annual Danish Astronomy Meeting 2023, June 2023, Fredericia, Denmark, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019641>, Poster.

2019

Herath, M., **Hinse, T. C.**, Gunesequera, S., Jayaratne, C., 2019, “*Observing exoplanets hosted by a binary system*”, European Planetary Science Congress, EPSC, 13, 847, Poster.

2018

Wood, J., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, S. C., 2018, “*Finding a Lower Bound on the Ring Limit for Planetary Close Encounters with Ringed Centaurs*”, AAS/Division for Planetary Sciences Meeting, 5030507, Poster.

Herath, M., **Hinse, T. C.**, Gunesequera, S., Jayaratne, C., 2018, “*Possible discovery of two Mini-Neptune type planets around a dim K-star*”, European Planetary Science Congress, EPSC, 12.244, Poster.

2017

Wood, Jeremy R., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, S., 2017, “*The Dynamical History of Chariklo and Its Rings*”, American Astronomical Society, DPS meeting 49, 221.04. Poster.

D'Aversa, E., Oliva, F., Sindoni, G., **Hinse, T. C.** et al., 2017, “*A stellar occultation by Ganymede*”, European Planetary Science Congress, EPSC. 11-850, Poster.

Hinse, T. C. et al., 2017, “*Observation of the 2016 Ganymede Stellar Occultation Event using the 0.6m SOAO Telescope*”, Bulletin of the Korean Astronomical Society, vol. 42, No. 2, SS-08. Korea Astronomical Society, Autumn Meeting, October 2017, Yeosu, Republic of Korea. Poster.

D'Aversa, E., et al. (incl. **Hinse, T. C.**), 2017, “*A 2016 Ganymede stellar occultation event*”, European Geophysical Union, General Assembly Meeting, EGUGA, 19, 5268, Poster.

2016

Kang, W., Kim, T., Kwon, S.-G., Lee, S.-G., **Hinse, T. C.**, 2016, “*Preliminary Results of Exoplanet Transit Observation by NYSC 1m Telescope*”, Korea Astr. Soc., Autumn Meeting, October 2016, National Scie. Museum, Daejeon, Republic of Korea. Poster.

Wood, Jeremy R., Horner, J., **Hinse, T. C.**, Marsden, S., 2016, “*The Dynamical Classification of Centaurs which Evolve into Comets*”, American Astronomical Society, DPS meeting 48, 120.23. Poster.

Beom-Kyu Choi, **Hinse, T. C.** & Tae-Seog Yoon, 2016, “*Orbital stability study and transit-timing variations of the extrasolar planetary system K2-3*”, Bulletin of the Korean Astronomical Society, vol. 41, No. 1, ST-12. Korea Astronomical Society, Spring Meeting, April 2016, Busan, Republic of Korea. Poster.

2015

Lee, J. W., **Hinse, T. C.**, Youn, J.-H., Han, W., August 2015, “*The Pulsating sdB+M Eclipsing System NY Virginis and its Circumbinary Planets*”, IAU General Assembly Meeting, AAS. Poster.

Hinse, T. C., July 2015, “*Dynamics & Synthetic Modelling of the Light-travel Time Effect of Circumbinary Extrasolar Planets*”, Carl Sagan Summer School Workshop, CalTech, Pasadena. Poster.

Baştürk, O., **Hinse, T. C.**, et al., July 2015, “*Defocused Observations of Selected Exoplanet Transits with T100 at the TÜBİTAK National Observatory of Turkey (TUG)*”, Living together: Planets, Host Stars and Binaries, Astronomical Society of the Pacific, Conference. Poster.

Hinse, T. C., April 2015, “*Development of a Prototype System for the Optical-Video-Detection and Characterisation of Meteors/Fireballs in South Korea*”, Spring 2015 meeting of the Korea Astronomical Society, Seoul National University, Seoul, Republic of Korea. Poster.

Hinse, T. C., April 2015, “*Development of a Prototype System for the Optical-Video-Detection and Characterisation of Meteors/Fireballs in South Korea*”, Spring 2015 meeting of the Korea Astronomical Society, Seoul National University, Seoul, Republic of Korea. Talk.

2014

Hinse, T. C., 2014, “*Stable 5-body dynamics of the Kepler-47 multi-planet system*”, Korea Astronomical Society, Autumn Meeting, October 2014, Jeju, Republic of Korea. Talk.

Basturk, O., **Hinse, T. C.**, et al., 2014, “*High precision defocused observations of planetary transits*”, Contributions of the Astronomical Observatory Skalnaté Pleso, vol. 43, no. 3, p. 402 – 407. Poster.

2013

Kim, M.-J., (including **Hinse, T. C.**) 2013, “*Rotational properties of Maria Asteroid Family*”, American Astronomical Society Meeting, Division of Planetary Science, #45, 304.08, Poster.

Hinse, T. C., 2013, “*Observations & Dynamics of Circumbinary Extrasolar Planets*”, MODEST-13 meeting, August 2013, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan. Talk.

Hinse, T. C., 2013, “*Observation and Dynamical Evolution of Jovian Irregular Satellites*”, Mini-workshop on Solar System Primitive Objects, June 2013, Seoul National University, Seoul, Republic of Korea. Talk.

Hinse, T. C., 2013, “*Photometric Follow-up Observations of Transiting Planets using Heavy Defocus Technique*”, Korea Astronomical Society, Spring Meeting, April 2013, Daecheon, Republic of Korea. Talk.

Hinse, T. C., 2013, “*Dynamics & Synthetic Modeling of the Light-travel Time Effect of Circumbinary Extrasolar Planets*”, IAUS 299 Symposium, Victoria, Canada, June 2013. Poster.

Horner, J. et al. (including **Hinse, T. C.**), 2013, “*Dynamical Constraints on Exoplanets*”, IAUS 299 Symposium, Victoria, Canada, June 2013. Poster.

Hinse, T. C., 2013, “*Observation and Dynamical Evolution of Jovian Irregular Satellites*”, Seoul National University, Mini-workshop on Solar system small bodies, June 2013, Seoul, Republic of Korea. Talk.

Satyral, S., Quarles, B., **Hinse, T. C.**, 2013, “*Assessment of Hill Stability Versus the Known Chaos Indicators*”, American Astronomical Society Meeting, January 2013, USA. Poster

Kostov, V. McCollough, P. R., **Hinse, T. C.**, et al. “*A Gas Giant Circumbinary Planet Transiting an Evolved F Star Primary of the Eclipsing Binary Star KIC 4862625 and the Independent Discovery and Characterization of the two transiting planets in the Kepler-47 System*”, American Astronomical Society Meeting, January 2013, USA. Poster.

2012

Hinse, T. C., 2012, “*Detection of additional planets around binary stars systems*”, Korea Astronomical Fall Meeting, October 2012 Gwangju, Republic of Korea. Talk.

Hinse, T. C., 2012, “*Prospects for the detection of additional planets around binary stars systems*”, IAU General Assembly Meeting, Beijing, China, September 2012. IAUS, 2014, 293, 133. Talk.

Lee, J. W., Lee, C.-U., Kim, S.-L., Kim, H.-I., Park, J.-H., **Hinse, T. C.**, 2012, “*Period Changes of the Algol System SZ Herculis*”, Conference Proceeding, IAUS, 282, 313. Poster.

2011

Hinse, T. C., Christou, A. A., 2011, “*Chaotic Long-term Dispersion of Jovian Retrograde Satellite Orbits*”, EPSC Conference Proceeding, Nantes, France. Poster.

2010

Hinse, T. C., Haghighipour, N., Gibson, N., 2010, “*Transit-timing variations and orbital stability of resonant high eccentric Earth-mass planets in "Hot Jupiter" systems*”, Proceeding of the conference: In the spirit of Lyot 2010, Paris. Poster.

2008

Hinse, T. C., Christou, A. A., 2008, “*Mapping Phase Space Topology Structure and Dynamics of Jovian Irregular Satellites*”, DPS, 40, 4606. Poster.

2005

Hinse, T. C., 2005, “*Particle Dynamics within the Habitable Zone of Extra Solar Planets*”, DPS, 37, 311. Poster.

Colloquium talks / various talks

Hinse, T. C., November 2015, “*Detection & dynamical aspects of extrasolar circumbinary companions/planets*”, Torun Centre for Astronomy, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland.

- Hinse, T. C.**, May 2015, “*Development of a proto-type system for the optical video detection and characterization of meteors/fireballs in South Korea*”, Korea Astronomical Society, bi-annual spring meeting, Seoul National University, South Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, December 2014, “*Detection & dynamical aspects of extrasolar circumbinary companions/planets*”, Institut for Astronomi, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark.
- Hinse, T. C.**, September 2014, “*5-body dynamics in the Kepler-47 System: Predicting Stable Orbits of a 3rd Circumbinary Planet*”, Korea Astronomical Society, bi-annual autumn meeting, Jeju, South Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, December 2014, “*Detection & dynamical aspects of extrasolar circumbinary companions/planets*”, Centre for Star and Planet Formation, Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Hinse, T. C.**, October 2013, “*Detection & dynamical aspects of extrasolar circumbinary companions/planets*”, German Aerospace Institute (DLR-Adlershof), Berlin, Germany.
- Hinse, T. C.**, November 2013, “*Detection & dynamical aspects of extrasolar circumbinary companions*”, India Institute of Astrophysics, Bangalore, India.
- Hinse, T. C.**, August 2013, “*Observations & Dynamics of Circumbinary Extrasolar Planets*”, MODEST-13 Conference, Almaty, Kazakhstan.
- Hinse, T. C.**, June 2013, “*Observation and Dynamical Evolution of Jovian Irregular Satellites*”, mini-workshop on solar system primitive objects, Seoul National University, South Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, May 2013, “*Photometric Follow-up Observations of Transiting Planets using Heavy Defocus Technique*”, Korea Astronomical Society, bi-annual spring meeting, Daecheon, South Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, December 2012, “*Detection, Modelling and Dynamics of Circumbinary Extrasolar Planets*”, NASA Center for Astrobiology, University of Hawaii, USA.
- Hinse, T. C.**, November 2012, “*Long-term Chaotic Diffusion of Jovian Irregular Satellite Orbits*”, lunch talk, Institute for Astronomy, University of Hawaii, USA.
- Hinse, T. C.**, October 2012, “*Dynamics of satellites and circumbinary extrasolar planets*”, Yonsei University Seoul, Republic of Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, July 2012, “*Circumbinary Planets from Ground-based Observations*”, Variable Objects meeting, KASI, Republic of Korea.
- Hinse, T. C.**, May 2012, “*Dynamics of Extrasolar Circumbinary Planets and their Detection using Light-travel time effect with ground-based Telescopes*”, Korea Astronomical Society meeting, Gwangju, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., July 2012, “*Chaotic Diffusion of Jovian Irregular Satellite Orbits*”, NASA Ames Research Center, California, USA.

Hinse, T. C., July 2012, “*Dynamics of Two-planet Circumbinary Systems*”, NASA Ames Research Center, California, USA.

Hinse, T. C., October 2011, “*Dynamics and Chaotic Long-Term Diffusion of Jovian Irregular Satellites – Implications for Solar System Giant Planet Formation*”, Centre for Star and Planet Formation, Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Hinse, T. C., June 2011, “*Photometric Follow-up of W Uma Type Eclipsing Binary RV Gruis (RV Gru)*”, MiNDSTeP collaboration, annual meeting, Doha, Qatar.

Hinse, T. C., May 2011, “*Chaotic Long-term Diffusion of Jovian Irregular Satellite Orbits*”, Purple Mountain Observatory, Nanjing, China.

Hinse, T. C., October 2010, “*Dynamical Aspects of Jovian Irregular Satellites. Chaotic long-term dispersion of retrograde satellite groups*”, Institute for Celestial Mechanics and Computation of Ephemerides, IMCCE, Paris, France.

Hinse, T. C., August 2007, “*Resonance Dynamics and Planet-Particle Dynamics within the Habitable Zones of Extrasolar Planetary Systems*”, Astronomical Science Group of Ireland annual meeting, Queens University Belfast, Belfast, UK.

Hinse, T. C., March 2006, “*Improving the microlensing early alert warning system for extrasolar planet search campaigns*”, SONG workshop, Aarhus University, Denmark.

(other talks given before 2011 are available upon request)

Popular Science Articles, Public Outreach, Media & Press

Since August 2022, I am uploading a lot of academic activities to zenodo. Click here for more details:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=Hinse&l=list&p=4&s=20&sort=bestmatch>

Hinse, T. C., Public outreach, “*The 2019 Transit of Mercury*”, Chungnam National University, November 2019, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Public outreach tour around Daejeon Planetarium & Observatory for SEM International, “*Ask an astronomer*”, Daejeon Planetarium & Observatory, July 2019, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Public outreach lecture, “*The Solar System: Life on other planets and moons?*”, Daejeon Planetarium & Observatory, February 2019, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Public outreach, “*Navigating Winter Night-sky: winter constellations and deep sky objects*”, Daejeon Planetarium & Observatory, February 2019, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Public outreach lecture, “*Practical Astronomy: Connecting with the Sky*”, Daejeon Planetarium & Observatory, January 2019, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*Astronomy, the Solar System and Extrasolar Planets*”, Taedeok Highschool, Daejeon, November 2018, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C. in “*Tracking the cosmic fireworks*” by Aswin Sekhar, News Laundry, August 2018. Interview/expert opinion.

URL: <https://www.newslaundry.com/2018/08/13/tracking-the-cosmic-fireworks-perseids-meteor-shower>.

Hinse, T. C. in “*A celestial treat: everything you need to know about the Perseids meteor shower*” by Aswin Sekhar, The News Minute India, August 2018. Interview/expert opinion.

URL: <https://www.thenewsminute.com/article/celestial-treat-everything-you-need-know-about-perseids-meteor-shower-86459>.

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*The Nature of Research in Astronomy and Space Science*”, Daejeon Christian International School, Daejeon, January 2018, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C. in “*The Sun Chasers*” by Aswin Sekhar, The Telegraph India, August 2017. Interview/expert opinion.

URL: https://www.telegraphindia.com/1170828/jsp/knowhow/story_169398.jsp

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*Galilei, dark matter and extrasolar planets*”, Jeonmin Highschool, Daejeon, November 2016, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Public Outreach: SEM - Daejeon Science Festival, 22. October 2016. “*Science & Research in Germany*”, Daejeon, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., “*This Jupiter-sized Planet Is the Largest Found Orbiting Two Suns – Any orbiting Moons could be habitable, but scientists have yet to spot them*” by Danny Lewis.

www.smithsonian.com, 14. June 2016. URL: <http://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/jupiter-sized-planet-largest-found-orbiting-two-suns-180959407/?no-ist>

Hinse, T. C., “*New Jupiter-like planet is largest yet discovered orbiting two stars - Spotted using data from the Kepler space telescope, the gas giant, dubbed Kepler-1647b, has one of the longest orbits recorded for a transiting planet*” by Nicola Davis, The Guardian, 13. June 2016. URL:

<https://www.theguardian.com/science/2016/jun/13/new-jupiter-like-planet-is-largest-yet-discovered-orbiting-two-stars-kepler-1647b>

Hinse, T. C., Press Release (In English): Armagh Observatory, NI, UK (2nd affiliation in 2016).

“*Astronomers Discover Large Circumbinary Planet In Habitable Zone*”. URL:

http://www.arm.ac.uk/press/2016/circumbinary_planet_June16_pr.html

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*Astronomy, the Solar System and Extrasolar Planets*”, Taedok Science Highschool, Daejeon, June 2016, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., *Public tour around KASI campus for Scientist and Engineers (SEM) in Daejeon. March 2016. Daejeon. Republic of Korea.*

Hinse, T. C., KASI Quarterly Magazine, “*Discovery of 10th Circumbinary Planet*”, Fall 2015, p. 12, vol. 19.

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Hinse, T. C., Popular science talk at Nicolai Copernicus Gymnasium, “*Astronomy, the Solar System & Extrasolar Planets*”, Torun, Poland, December 2015.

Hinse, T. C., KASI Quarterly Magazine, “*Research & Education program: Building a prototype double-station meteor detection camera system in Korea*”, Winter 2015, p. 20.

Hinse, T. C., Daejeon Ilbo Newspaper, “*Building a Meteor Detection System in South Korea*”, http://www.daejonilbo.com/news/newsitem.asp?pk_no=1191306, October 2015.

Hinse, T. C., KAIST podcast/interview by Prof. Tim Thompson (KAIST) - “*Around the Carillon*”, URL: <http://www.kaist.edu/html/en/news/podcast.html>, 2015, Season 3, Episode 8, On: Extrasolar planet research at KASI, Daejeon, KAIST, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*Astronomien, solsystemet og planeter omkring andre stjerner*”, Uffe-Skolen Toenning, December 2014, Germany.

Hinse, T. C., Korean Dong-A Popular Science Magazine on “*Irregular Satellites in the Solar System*”, DONG-A, URL: <http://www.dongascience.com/>, Seoul, 2014.

Horner, J., Wittenmyer, R.A., Marshall, J.P., **Hinse, T. C.**, Robertson, P., “*Testing proposed planetary systems – to destruction*”, A&G (New and Reviews in Astronomy & Geophysics), 2014, Vol. 55, Issue 4, pp. 4.30 – 4.35.

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Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk, “*Astronomy, the Solar System and Extrasolar Planets*”, Daejeon Science Highschool, Daejeon, Novmber 2013, South Korea.

Hinse, T. C., “*Spectacular Rendevous on the Sky*”, The Korea Herald, June 3, 2012
URL: www.koreaherald.com/view.php?ud=20120603000360

Hinse, T. C., Popular Science Talk at Nykoebing Realskole, “*Astronomien, Solsystemet og Extrasolare Planeter*”, October 2011, Nykoebing, Denmark.

Hinse, T. C. & Michelsen, R., (in danish). “*Jordens mærkelige følgesvende – opdagelsen af Jordens første trojanske asteroide*”, Kvant No. 1, 2012.

URL: <http://www.kvant.dk/issue.php?n=1&y=2012>

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